

Kinetics and mechanism of *N*-bromosuccinimide oxidation of L-arginine in aqueous acidic medium

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The title reaction is of first order in [*N*-bromosuccinimide], fractional order in [L-Arginine] and of inverse fractional order in [H⁺]. The added products, ionic strength and dielectric constant on the reaction rate have no effect. A mechanism involving the unprotonated NBS species as the reactive species of the oxidant has been proposed. The reaction constants involved in the mechanism are derived. The activation parameters are computed with respect to slow step of the mechanism.

N-Bromosuccinimide is a source of positive halogen, and this reagent has been exploited¹ as oxidant for a variety of substrates in both acidic and alkaline medium. The use of *N*-bromosuccinimide as an oxidant in acidic medium is extensive² and it has also been used in the determination of some organic compounds³. Arginine is one of the essential amino acids. In the present work, the kinetics of oxidation of L-arginine by *N*-bromosuccinimide in presence of mercury(II) acetate⁴ in perchloric acid medium have been studied with a view to elucidate the mechanism of the reaction and to identify the reactive species of the oxidant in acid medium.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry and reaction products : Different sets of reaction mixtures containing different quantities of NBS and L-arginine at constant [H⁺] and ionic strength were reacted for 24 h at 26° and then analyzed. The remaining NBS was assayed iodometrically⁵. The oxidation products were identified as succinimide and aldehyde⁶ by their respective spot tests; the presence of the corresponding aldehyde, 4-guanidinobutanaldehyde was also confirmed by silver mirror test. The results are in agreement with 1 : 1 stoichiometry,

It was observed that the aldehyde does not undergo further oxidation under the present kinetic conditions, since the test for the corresponding acid⁶, the probable oxidation product of aldehyde, was found negative.

Reaction order : The reaction orders were determined

from the slopes of log k_{obs} vs log (concentration) plots by varying the concentration of oxidant, reductant and acid in turn while keeping others constant. The linearity of plots of log [NBS] vs time indicates the order in [NBS] as unity, this was also confirmed by constant values of k_{obs} at varying [NBS]. The order in [L-arg] was found to be fractional and the order in [H⁺] inverse fractional (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of variation of [NBS], [L-arg] and [H⁺] on oxidation of L-arginine by *N*-bromosuccinimide in aqueous acid medium

Temp. = 26°, I = 0.30 mol dm ⁻³			$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	
[NBS] × 10 ³	[L-arg] × 10 ²	[H ⁺]	Expt.	Calcd.*
mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³		
0.3	2.0	0.10	2.93	3.07
0.5	2.0	0.10	2.90	3.07
1.0	2.0	0.10	2.95	3.07
3.0	2.0	0.10	2.95	3.07
5.0	2.0	0.10	2.85	3.07
1.0	0.3	0.10	0.61	0.62
1.0	1.0	0.10	1.80	1.80
1.0	2.0	0.10	2.95	3.07
1.0	2.5	0.10	3.55	3.57
1.0	3.0	0.10	3.96	4.00
1.0	2.0	0.05	3.69	3.80
1.0	2.0	0.07	3.38	3.47
1.0	2.0	0.10	2.95	3.07
1.0	2.0	0.30	1.60	1.73
1.0	2.0	0.50	1.20	1.21

*Rate constants were calculated using values of k , K_1 and K_2 as $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, 12.5 mol dm^{-3} and $50.0 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. Error : ±5%.

Effect of mercury(II) acetate : The effect of concentration of mercury(II) acetate⁴ observed in the range 0.02–0.1 mol dm⁻³, was found to be negligible on the rates of reaction. The function of added mercuric acetate is therefore only to fix up Br⁻ formed in the course of reaction as HgBr₂ or HgBr₄²⁻.

Effect of products : The effect of product, succinimide, was studied in the concentration range $(0.50-10.0) \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³. The added product had negligible effect on the rates of reaction.

The effect of changing the dielectric constant in the reaction medium was studied by adding acetic acid (5–30%) in the reaction medium at constant concentrations of other reactants. The effect was found to be negligible on the rate of reaction. The effect of ionic strength was studied by varying the concentration of NaClO₄ in the reaction medium. It was found that the rate of reaction is independent of ionic strength of the medium.

The reaction mixture was kept for 24 h with acrylonitrile in an inert atmosphere. Test for free radical was negative.

Effect of temperature : The rate of reaction was measured at different temperatures under varying [L-arg]. The rate constants (*k*) of the slow step (Scheme 1) were calculated from intercepts of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{L-arg}]$ plots for different temperatures (26, 31 and 36°) and used to calculate the activation parameters. The ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values obtained were 84 ± 2 kJ mol⁻¹ and -17 ± 4 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively.

Mechanism : It is known⁷ that the probable reactive species of NBS in acid solution are $>\text{NBr}$, HOBr, $>\text{N}^+\text{HBr}$, H₂OBr⁻. The reaction is first order in [NBS] and fractional order in [L-arg], while inverse fractional order in [H⁺]. The inhibition nature of addition of H⁺ ions on rate may be explained by assuming the equilibria (I \rightleftharpoons II) to be present and that the unprotonated species (I) is the reactive one,

The order of less than unity in [L-arg] reveals the possibility of involvement of complex formation in the reaction system in pre-equilibrium. Attempts to obtain spectral evidence were in vain, and there was no appreciable change in the spectra of L-arginine and NBS in presence of an acid. A feeble interaction is probably involved. However, evidence for the complex formation is obtained kinetically. Such complex formation between oxidant and substrate was observed in earlier studies⁸.

L-Arginine in aqueous solution exists as zwitterion. However, in strongly acidic medium, it exists in the protonated form. It is known that NBS serves as a source of bromonium ion (Br⁺) and undergoes a simple two-electron reduction leading to the formation of bromide ion, succinimide and the products of reaction⁴. The NBS as a source of bromonium ion gives product Br⁻ in presence of mercuric acetate. The unprotonated NBS (discussed elsewhere) reacts with protonated L-arginine to form a complex

which decomposes in a slow step followed by fast step to give products as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Scheme 1 leads to rate law (1),

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{k K_2 [\text{NBS}] [\text{L-arg}]}{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_2 [\text{L-arg}]} \quad (1)$$

Strictly, the factor, $1 + K_2 [\text{NBS}]$ should also be included in the denominator on the right-hand-side of the equation, but in view of the low concentration of NBS used, it approximates to unity. Equation (1) may be transformed to equation (2) which is suitable for verification,

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k K_2 [\text{L-arg}]} + \frac{K_1 [\text{H}^+]}{k K_2 [\text{L-arg}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (2)$$

According to equation (2), the plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{L-arg}]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$ are linear with non-zero intercept and the plots were found to be so (figures not shown). From the slopes and intercepts of such plots, *k*, *K*₁ and *K*₂ values are obtained (at 26°) as 1×10^{-3} s⁻¹, 12.5 mol dm⁻³ and 50.0 dm³ mol⁻¹ respectively. Using these values the calculated rate constants are in reasonable agreement with the experimental ones under different conditions of experiments (Table 1).

The negligible effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant might be due to involvement of neutral species in the reaction. The modest energy of activation and entropy of activation suggest the involvement of complex transition state in the reaction⁹.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout. Aqueous solutions of NBS³ (s.d. fine), L-arginine (s.d. fine) and mercury(II) were prepared. The succinimide was prepared¹⁰ and crystallized. Perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate were used to maintain the required acidity and ionic strength respectively.

Kinetic runs : Kinetic runs were followed under pseudo-first order condition, where [L-arg] was at least ten-fold excess over [NBS] at constant ionic strength of 0.30 mol dm⁻³ at 26.0 ± 0.1°. The reaction was initiated by mixing the thermally equilibrated solutions of NBS containing 0.02 mol dm⁻³ Hg(OAc)₂ and L-arginine, which contained the required quantities of perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate. The progress of reaction was followed by estimating the change in concentration of NBS at regular intervals of time, iodometrically⁶. The first order rate constant (k_{obs}) was evaluated by plots of log [NBS] vs time. Such plots in almost all cases were linear upto more than 80% of completion of reaction; k_{obs} values were reproducible within ±5%.

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